

PETROGENESIS OF LUNAR FAR SIDE HIGHLAND LITHOLOGIES: IMPLICATIONS FOR LUNAR CRUST FORMATION. Jiaqi Zheng¹, Qi He¹, Zaicong Wang¹, Jun Huang¹, J. F. Pernet-Fisher², Yiheng Li¹, Xu Chen¹, Keqing Zong¹, Ioannis Baziotis³, Jiannan Zhao¹, Long Xiao¹, and Zhenbing She¹. ¹State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources, Hubei Provincial Key Laboratory of Planetary Geology and Deep-Space Exploration, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, People's Republic of China. ²Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Manchester, Manchester, M13 9PL, UK. ³Department of Natural Resources Management & Agricultural Engineering, Agricultural University of Athens, Iera Odos 75, Athens 11855, Athens, Greece (jiaqizheng@cug.edu.cn)

Introduction: The Chang'e-6 (CE-6) mission successfully returned lunar soil samples from the farside of the Moon in June 2024, marking the first-ever sample return from this region. The collected material originated from a mare basalt area in the southern Apollo basin, located within the South Pole–Aitken basin. Preliminary characterization results reveal that, in addition to mare basalts, the CE-6 lunar soil also contains a considerable proportion of nonmare materials, such as anorthosites, norites, and troctolites. These nonmare materials - particularly anorthosites offer a valuable opportunity to investigate the composition of the farside lunar crust and how it differs from that of the nearside. Moreover, they have the potential to provide key insights into the different proposed mechanism driving the lunar crustal formation as summarized above.

Samples and Analytical Methods: Four lithic clasts (two anorthosite clasts, one norite clast and one noritic anorthosite clast) from the scooped CE-6 soil (CE6C0200YJFM003, 500mg) obtained from the China National Space Administration Agency were investigated.

The lithic fragments were analyzed by the TESCAN Integrated Mineral Analyzer system (TIMA3 XGHM) at China University of Geosciences, Wuhan. Mineral major-element compositions were determined using a JEOL JXA-8230 electron microprobe analyzer (EPMA) at GPMR-CUG. Trace-element analyses were obtained using an Agilent 7500a ICP-MS coupled with a Geolas 2005 excimer ArF laser (193nm) ablation system (Lambda Physik, Göttingen, Germany).

Petrography and Geochemistry: Here we report two anorthosite clast, one norite clast, and one noritic anorthosite clast (Fig.1). The two FANs contain <10 modal% mafic phases. The two noritic clasts are enriched in mafic minerals relative to anorthosites; the one with a higher modal (68.2%) content of plagioclase is classified as a noritic anorthosite.

The rare earth element compositions of minerals were analyzed, alongside a few other examples of Apollo samples. In general, the REE patterns of plagioclase and low-Ca pyroxene reported here are within the range of plagioclase REE compositions reported from lunar anorthositic meteorites and Apollo FANs^[1-5].

Figure 1: BSE images of noritic anorthosite and FAN clasts from CE-6 soil. (a) Noritic anorthosite (clast 4–28); (b) norite (clast 5–48); (c) anorthosite (clast 12–1); (d) anorthosite (clast 1–175). Mineral abbreviations: Opx—orthopyroxene; Pl—plagioclase; Aug—augite; Cpx—low-Ca pyroxene; Tro—troilite; Ilm—ilmenite.

Discussion: Plagioclase REE abundances are not significantly affected by diffusive equilibration^{[6][7]}. As such, REE compositions of liquids that may have been in equilibrium with this mineral can be calculated to assess partial melt compositions of the clasts investigated here. Thermodynamic modeling by S. M. Elardo & D. F. Astudillo Manosalva (2023)^[8] and T. C. Prissel & J. Gross (2020)^[9] demonstrates that KREEP-free Mg-suite lithologies are expected to crystallize plagioclase with high An contents and mafic minerals with Mg# values comparable to those observed in noritic anorthosite clast. To explore the genetic relationships between KREEP-free/poor Mg-suite lithologies and noritic anorthosite clast, we modeled trace element partitioning during mantle melting and fractional crystallization (Fig.1). Results show that REE contents can be reproduced by ~90% fractional crystallization of olivine and plagioclase from a primary

melt generated by 0.5%-1% partial melting of a KREEP-free mantle source.

Figure 2: Parental melts of KREEP-poor rocks of REE modeling and chondrite-normalized REE patterns for a KREEP-free LPUM during partial melting and fractional crystallization.

Conclusion: CE-6 samples indicate that the farside crust formed contemporaneously with the nearside during the final stages of LMO solidification. FAN clasts from the farside have mineral and chemical characteristics indistinguishable from Apollo nearside FANs, confirming a global distribution of ferroan anorthosites. The noritic anorthosite may represent a KREEP-free or KREEP-poor Mg-suite lithology, formed by low-degree partial melting ($\sim 0.5\text{--}1\%$) of deep LMO cumulates followed by $\sim 90\%$ fractional crystallization. Modeling suggests a minor (5–15%) KREEP assimilation could explain its REE enrichment. the lunar crust formation was a global, synchronized event, followed by localized magmatic and impact reworking. Later intrusive or impact-related processes modified portions of the crust, but did not erase its primary anorthositic composition.

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